

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: OKBAZGI****FIRST NAME: ANDEBRHAN****PROGRAM CODE: DIPH****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: PERIOD 1****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

FUNDAMENTALS OF WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

The coursepack for period one (1) starts by introducing what an essay paper should look like and the contents of such an essay, the steps one should follow while preparing an essay are extensively explained. This course pack also talks about plagiarism, some rules for writing paper, style guide, the difference in American and British English, punctuations and dates, and about Chicago Manual of Style, and other basics. I feel Euclid university wants their student to be on board while writing a paper by introducing even the basics of writing style that most of them have forgotten or otherwise. Such problems are common in many students which most of us refer back while confronting with difficulties during writing.

2) ESSAY WRITING

Generally, there are seven steps that should be considered in preparing an essay (EUCLID 2015, 1-5). I find it very practical which are basic issues that one should follow for a good essay writing. Writing everything you know is only an initial step which leads you to further question yourself and make research about the topic of interest (EUCLID 2015, 2). It is very interesting for me, the questions that one should have to ask him/herself while preparing an essay that would help in exploring everything possible to answer the essay question and ensure that you are on the right track to provide evidence in favor or against the hypothesis raised. Moreover, I find it new that I did not think of it before in a standard form on the content of each essay paragraph in the body section of the essay that should revolve around one main point by including the topic sentence, supporting sentence, evidence and analysis (EUCLID 2015, 4).

3) AMERICAN VERSUS BRITISH ENGLISH

I usually struggle to differentiate a Standard American English (SAE) and Standard British English (SBE), which this document emphasized for being consistent in one document and not to mix both styles. The difference in sociolectic value between SAE and SBE should be considered well however, it is difficult to understand for people who speak English as second language (EUCLID 2015, 54). Understanding both ways is very important to stick in one style for consistency purposes which is more convenient for you. There is a means of preparing one document in a consistent way (either US or UK spelling) by the help of Microsoft Office word applying set proofing language (EUCLID 2019, 6:08).

4) PLAGIARISM

I find very important the way plagiarism is discussed in order to escape from academic penalty. More emphasis is given to the essence of providing credit to owner of the information you are using and proper citation as a means of avoiding plagiarism (EUCLID 2015, 13). Using some one's information without proper citation and handing over other's work as if you have prepared it is considered plagiarism (EUCLID 2015, 10). In-text citation and list of works cited are among the methods of citation where I had little knowledge in my previous studies, but I got it very helpful to apply them properly (EUCLID 2015, 15). In-text citation it-self can be placed either as quotation which is advised for limited usage or paraphrases (EUCLID 2015, 18 & 22). In applying paraphrases putting the ideas in your own words and using different style represent the accurate information of the original ideas are among the points that must be considered (EUCLID 2015, 24). Everything that is said by others may not need citation as this information can be generally known ideas which are commonly placed in many other literatures (EUCLID 2015, 30). I am previously slightly informed about the list of works cited which is a bibliography or reference of works but with limited knowledge about its basic format.

5) STYLE GUIDE

I agree to follow a fixed style of writing (style guide) because, for purposes of consistency and coherence it is specially very helpful when a document is jointly developed by many authors (EUCLID 2015, 52). The Chicago Manual of Style (CMS) which deals with Chicago Style & Usage, Chicago Page Formatting and Chicago End/Footnotes are among the notes that I did not prepared a paper following such recognized style but simply doing it as I feel right. I have come across many words and sentences expressed in capitalization, italics/quotes and formatted as compound words in many documents however, I have never thought of whether there is standard way of style and usage which I simply supposed it as a writer's style.

6) FUNDAMENTALS

I find the usage of punctuations and dates very interesting which I have never seen it seriously. Putting dates in a way that avoids confusion between days and months is very important. The US and GB uses different style to quote a remark using quotation mark “ ” and inverted commas ‘ ’ respectively (EUCLID 2015, 59). Moreover, US fixed standards places periods and commas inside quotation marks while FIN/GB procedure places in either inside or outside the closing quotation marks (EUCLID 2015, 59).

The use of s’ and ‘s which I remember learning in high school but found difficult at later stages were among the points I got important to revise and use them properly. The application of ‘s and s’ have some exceptions to avoid too many “s” sounds and this could confuse readers (EUCLID 2015, 47). Moreover, I find very important the application of possessive form and contraction of words which leads to some confusion for some readers. Example: - its and it’s, your and you’re (EUCLID 2015, 47).

I usually find the use of comma before the “and” in the list of items in various literatures however, there were literature that do not use comma before “and,” but I have never realized what actually the formal and modern way of using it. Though, both ways are acceptable, to avoid confusion and for the interest of consistency it is advisable to use comma before the “and” (EUCLID 2015, 48).

The way papers are corrected is provided on sample corrections to papers which are very helpful and consider them while doing the same task. Writers can vary in the way of expressing ideas however, expressing more formally could provide more sense and engagement to the reader.

Previously, I did not suppose them as Latin words but only used to know the meaning of the abbreviations provided in this manual such as e.g., etc., i.e., and others. The common Latin abbreviations used in writing provided me a very good chance to be aware of the abbreviations that I would face in different documents and to use them appropriately when applicable. In my earlier papers, I only tried to be consistent in expressing numbers in text which this document clearly noted the choice between spelling out a number and using numerals. I find the detailed guidance provided how to put numbers very helpful.

7) CONCLUSION

This document reminds me a lot about the basics that I have learnt early during my English freshman program in the university. Generally, I found a lot of new practices and usage to be followed, especially from the CMS Crib Sheet that would be used for a reference while doing papers from now onwards. I appreciate all the points described here even some of them are refreshing my knowledge. This would help me in preparing my papers in a standard way which follow a consistent style and critically correct other papers.

REFERENCES

EUCLID. 2015. *ACA-401 Coursepack Period 1*. Retrieved from: <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1/>.

EUCLID. 2019. *Understanding templates and styles for ACA-401*. Retrieved from: <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1/>.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.